

WHAT TO EXPECT AT A VEIN TREATMENT LINDENHURST

vein treatment Lindenhurst will evaluate your medical history at the first consultation. By conducting a physical exam they will discuss your symptoms and concerns. To determine your specific vein condition, an ultrasound is conducted at the first visit. The vein doctor will discuss the diagnosis and may recommend a treatment plan which is best suitable for you.

[vein doctor Lindenhurst](#) will recommend vein treatments that include Endovenous laser therapy(EVLT), stab phlebectomy, or sclerotherapy.

Endovenous Laser Therapy (EVLT)

It is a procedure that is used to treat varicose veins. This surgery involves a thin fiber that is inserted into your vein and used a laser to seal the damaged vein. From the damaged veins, the blood is being diverted to the normal veins with functional valves that will improve the circulation of blood.

This laser procedure only requires local anesthesia and takes less than an hour. It improves the appearance and gives immediate relief from symptoms. After the completion of the procedure, you can resume daily activities immediately.

Phlebectomy

It is a type of vein treatment that is used to remove the varicose veins which are shown on the surface of the legs. This procedure makes cuts of approximately two millimeters in size on the skin, through which varicose veins are removed. In this procedure, there will be no

requirement of the stitches, and can be done at [varicose vein treatment Lindenhurst](#) with the help of local anesthesia. It will also help to improve the appearance of your legs.

Stab phlebectomy treats the varicose veins on the surface of the leg. Depending on the patient's needs, it can be combined with the other varicose veins treatment.

Sclerotherapy

In the early stages of spider veins and small varicose veins, this procedure is being used to treat them. This helps in preventing future complications. This process is done with the help of a needle through which a solution is injected inside the veins results in the inflammation of veins. This causes veins to collapse and then they eventually close. To hold the vein together patients have to wear a wrap for some days.

This process helps in the redirection of blood flow through the healthy veins. The remaining damaged veins are absorbed by the body over time. Sometimes you may need a number of only injections while other times you required sclerotherapy sessions depending on your veins. These numbers may vary according to the type of veins and the number of veins being treated. After having surgery or the procedure you can immediately resume normal activities.

Cost of vein treatment at Lindenhurst

The cost of vein treatments Lindenhurst depends on the severity and type of treatment you are getting. We will work with all major insurance companies and speak to your carrier for the best possible coverage that you will receive. This will help in minimizing your out-of-pocket expenses. In case, if you dont have medical insurance coverage then to cover your varicose vein treatment, a reputable Suffolk county near you will provide several payment plans to you.